

History and Development Process of Family Counseling in the World and Turkey

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ABSTRACT

Of this article , the definition of family development process of families throughout history , the definition , scope oath purpose of family counseling , the difference from family therapist , the functioning of family counseling in the world and in Turkey , the conditions for becoming a family counsellor in Turkey oath the

importance of family counseling in Turkey oath the world are examined the development process of family counseling has been examined and it has been concluded that it has an important place in the world and in Turkey .

Keywords : Family , Counselling , Social , Psychology , Behavior , Therapy , Problems

INTRODUCTION

The family, which is formed by the marital unit, is the most compact social unit in existence. The family institution has a historical background of about 4000 years (Özgülven, 2009, p.25).

While this notion serves as the foundation of society, it may also harbor inherent issues. The shift from traditional civilizations to contemporary societies has brought about alterations and revolutions in the family institution, leading to the emergence of novel perspectives and lifestyles in family relationships. The alterations and conversions have resulted in

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communication difficulties within the family. Instances of family counseling practice have arisen due to various factors, including communication issues among spouses, challenges stemming from parental aging, insufficient communication between parents and children, marital disagreements, divorce, and shifts in marital structures. These problems have prompted the need for family counseling as a means to address and resolve them. This research aims to analyze the historical and developmental aspects of family counseling both globally and specifically in Turkey.

AIM

The objective is to examine the global and Turkish family counseling system, including its structure, operation, limitations, historical evolution in different nations, and recent advancements in Turkey.

METHOD

This page is a collection that follows the Qualitative research technique. It gathers academic publications, symposiums, research results, and academic material from books on family counseling worldwide, including Turkey.

RESULTS

Both family structure and family dynamics have undergone transformations. New family counseling ideas have arisen in conjunction with traditional treatments in this instance. This research aimed to assess the effectiveness of the short-term solution-oriented approach, a postmodern method, in the context of family therapy. Therefore, an endeavor was undertaken to ascertain the philosophical dimension, viewpoint, and therapeutic strategy of this technique. The relevance of postmodern methods is heightened by their characteristics of economy, pragmatism, and short duration, which are often favored. The document evaluation revealed

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that the approaches of this approach are often used. Despite its recent popularity, there is a lack of informative and developmental research in the literature. This analysis explores the dynamic structure of family counseling services, the concept of family and its evolution, family counseling and development, the theoretical and philosophical foundations of Solution-Focused Short-Term Family Counseling as a postmodern approach, the established therapeutic relationship, the techniques employed in the approach, and the strengths and limitations of the approach. This research, which is literature-based, found that the fundamental features of the short-term solution-oriented approach are applicable to family therapy as well. This strategy prioritizes future-oriented decision-making and growth, without taking previous experiences into consideration. Consequently, using a short-term solution-focused strategy in family therapy might be advantageous due to its cost-effectiveness, time efficiency, and ability to provide outcomes within a shorter timeframe.

The influence of postmodernism may be seen in several domains, including art, philosophy, architecture, and psychology. In the field of family therapy, postmodernist ideas have evolved as a response to these influences. The primary impact of postmodernism in psychology is the replacement of the comprehension of objective reality and counselor-centered procedures with an understanding of reality that is mostly influenced by socio-cultural elements and client-centered approaches (Dyck, 2000). The prevailing theories in contemporary family therapy are Narrative Therapy and Solution-Focused Short-Term Family therapy (Nazlı, 2018). This research aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of Solution-Focused Short-Term Family Counseling.

WHAT IS FAMILY?

The presence of many family configurations in our contemporary society poses challenges in establishing a universally applicable definition of family. Therefore, when examining the family, it is more useful to focus on its specific attributes rather than attempting to provide a broad definition. These attributes include the number of households, the quality of the household, communication patterns within the family, kinship relations, blood and lineage

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connections, socialization practices, and economic structure. Each of these aspects can be studied independently. Therefore, it can be seen that the family is a comprehensive and organized entity. The family, consisting of the marital bond between a husband and wife, as well as the relationship between parents and children, plays a significant role in society.

The family, which is the fundamental and most basic unit of society, originated with the advent of human existence and the cohabitation of humans. Furthermore, it establishes the practice of cohabitation as a formalized arrangement. The family has undergone substantial transformations throughout the course of history. The transition from the extended family to the nuclear family signifies the occurrence of this shift.

Kandiyoti (1984) argues that the inclusion of women in the workforce has led to a redistribution of responsibilities for child rearing, childcare, and household chores between couples. As a result, traditional domestic roles have shifted, and additional duties have been taken on by both partners (Algan 2016).

According to Yörükoğlu (2007), nuclear families experience greater isolation, lack support, and are in a more precarious and vulnerable position compared to extended families. Consequently, spouses who are unprepared to assume responsibilities in such families are prone to experiencing frequent role conflicts and interpersonal problems. We may analyze the evolution of family structures across five distinct categories, spanning from the past to the present.

These.

- 1-Family in Historical Process
- 2-Family in the Hunter and Gatherer Society
- 3-Family in Agricultural Society
- 4-Family in Industrial Society
- 5- It is the family in the post-industrial society.

Family in Historical Process

The institution of the family has a historical lineage spanning around 4000 years. Throughout history, the definition, kinds, functions, and structure of the notion of family have evolved and transformed in response to changes in relationships. (Köse, 2016, pages 15-16).

Family in a Hunter and Gatherer Society

During the early stages of human civilization, the primary focus revolved on the relentless pursuit of survival. A fundamental role of the family is to cohabitate. The act of cohabitation was founded upon several factors including social, economic, religious, protective, and security considerations, with the primary emphasis being on productivity (Özgüven, 2009, p.25).

It is well acknowledged that hunting and gathering cultures had a matriarchal structure. In matriarchal civilizations, the establishment of family systems occurred when lineage was ascertained based on the mother. These civilizations also recognize the significance of women's division of labor and responsibilities in the manufacturing process. (Köse, 2016, page 16).

Family in Agricultural Society

Men, who engaged in hunting before to the advent of agriculture, assumed a more prominent position in the production process by acquiring the skills to grow and harvest crops in the field. Within these cultures, the economy centered upon manufacturing, which created a need for individuals to remain within their own families. Women in such marriages were required to relocate to their husbands' residences and live with them. Consequently, this resulted in the emergence of big households. Occupations within the family are assigned based on biological sex. The reliance on land also resulted in the establishment of a stable social structure (Baran and Atlı, 2016, p. 37).

Family in Industrial Society

The industrial revolution had a significant impact on family structures. Following the industrial revolution, modest agricultural plots and fields were replaced by factories and large-scale industries. Industrialization spurred urbanization, prompting many families to abandon their rural holdings and relocate to metropolitan regions to seek employment in industries (Zastrow, 2014, p.259).

Factories are the primary and crucial instruments of production in these civilizations. In industrial societies, nuclear family arrangements including of parents and children have become prevalent. The patriarchal family structure persisted throughout this time, similar to the agrarian culture (Köse, 2016, p.16).

Family in Post-Industrial Society

The 1980s saw swift changes that exposed a transition in the economic framework from the industrial sector to the service sector. The increased participation of women in the service sector has resulted in alterations to the dynamics of family interactions. The issue of equality in family relationships has started to gain prominence (Köse, 2016, p.16).

Nevertheless, shifts in the personal realm have led to substantial alterations in how people understand the institution of marriage and family. The growth of alternative lifestyles and new family patterns for marriage and family has been a result of this (Köse, 2016, p.16).

Development Process in Turkish Family Structure

The Turkish family system may be analyzed in three distinct time periods (Baran and Atli, 2016, p.39-41). These items:

During the Pre-Islamic Period, Turks placed great importance on family order and home life (Bayır, 2016, p. 12). This time is characterized by the practice of monogamous marriage. The nuclear family arrangement is prevalent. Gender equality is maintained between women and men (Baran and Atli, 2016, p.39-41). While monogamy was prevalent in ancient Turkish

society, polygamous marriages were seldom seen as well (Özgür Bayır, 2016, p. 12).

2) Post-Islamic Period: During this era, significant alterations emerged in the Turkish family framework. The fundamental transformation had place throughout the Ottoman Era. The prevalence of "extended family" was pervasive under the Ottoman Empire, mostly as a result of the land system and economic structure's effect. Islam regards the family as the fundamental basis of society. (Baran and Atlı, 2016, pages 39-41; Özgür Bayır, 2016, page 12). The Tanzimat reforms transformed the family structure that confined women to the roles of "woman" and "mother" inside the household, and instead allowed women to engage with the outside world (Baran and Atlı, 2016, pp. 39-41).

During the Republican era, the family structure underwent changes in conjunction with socio-economic and cultural transformations (Özgür Bayır, 2016, p.12). The establishment of equality between men and women began with the enactment of the "Civil Code" in 1926. Women were granted suffrage in 1930. Urban areas saw the emergence of nuclear families. The demographic composition of rural areas, which was mostly focused on agriculture, has undergone a significant shift towards an industrial and urban framework (Baran and Atlı, 2016, p.39-41). This transformation has also given rise to a new family unit known as the "shantytown family". These households, sometimes referred to as "temporary extended family," exhibit rural (agricultural) traits and have also experienced the impacts of the changes introduced by the new texture (Özgür Bayır, 2016, p.12).

The 3rd Family Council (1998) highlighted that the family institution has undergone changes due to several circumstances, including evolving living conditions, technological advancements, and the economic situations of both industrialized and developing nations. Furthermore, it is said that globalization, modernity, individualization, secularism, and urbanization, which operate within a cause-and-effect framework, are the primary catalysts for these developments. The graphic indicates that various family kinds, including single-parent families, families with just one kid, cohabiting couples, rising divorce rates, declining marriage rates, and a rise in children born out of wedlock, have an influence on family models (Algan 2016).

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These changes have resulted in a range of issues inside the family, causing formerly healthy family members to become unwell and preventing families from completely or partly carrying out their roles and responsibilities (Algan, 2016).

Naztiya has initiated a needs assessment technique to address and eliminate the current challenges faced by families who are socially isolated in contemporary society.

1- Family counseling and therapy services for counseling and treatment.

2-Educational Services (Family Life Education)

3- Family Court Advocacy Services

The objective of these research is to identify remedies for the challenges arising from societal changes inside the family unit.

Although Sigmund Freud was the first individual to investigate family dynamics, it was his daughter, Alfred Adler, who delved into the intricacies of the family structure.

One of the key social factors in the field of family therapy is the inclusion of individuals with a familial predisposition to schizophrenia. World War II is the third component. World War II caused significant hardship for several families, leaving them in dire need of assistance. The National Mental Agreement, formed in 1946, expedited research on mental health (Gadding 1998).

During the 1960s, there were significant advancements in the realm of counseling and therapy. Notable figures from this era include Jag Hay, Virginia Satir, S. Minuchin, and J. Bell. Additionally, N. Akerman, C. Writokor, and Murray Bowen are all mentioned at this time (Algan, 2016).

By the 1970s, family counseling ideas had grown more organized and structured. Once again, at this time, the influence of religions on science also impacts scientists. Yalom and colleagues. According to Algan (2016), family guidance movements lack a comprehensive and consistent foundation.

The initiation of family therapy in Turkey occurred at a later time compared to western nations.

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In the 1980s, institutions started offering courses on "Family Therapy" in response to the growing interest in this field (Korkut, 2001, p115).

The "Family Counseling" service, launched by the Family Planning Association in Turkey in 1983, is regarded as the pioneering effort in this domain (Güran 1983, p.20).

During the 1990s, there was a rise in specialized knowledge and novel ideas related to Family Counseling. The citation is from the book "Özabacı Erkan" published in 2014, on page 31.

Since the year 2000 and onwards, family therapy has gained global recognition and has been implemented in a structured manner (Algan, 2016).

DEFINITION, PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF FAMILY COUNSELING

Family therapy encompasses a wide range of themes. In 1991, Kuzgun defined family counseling as the provision of psychological support to family members with the aim of fostering a harmonious atmosphere among them (Karataş, 2016).

Family therapy primarily focuses on reforming the family structure, but it also addresses divorce and post-divorce processes as significant topics (Karataş, 2016).

Family counselors assist in enhancing family ties and managing challenging situations such as sickness, divorce, and bereavement.

Another principle used in this domain is family therapy. The Ministry of Family and Social Services (2011) seeks to use family therapy to identify the dynamics of family members' interactions and comprehend the unhealthy patterns that arise within the relationship system. It modifies dysfunctional patterns of interaction. Additionally, it is said that the family has the objective of cultivating problem-solving abilities.

According to Korkut (2001), differentiating between family counseling and family therapy is a challenging task.

Furthermore, the 2011 report from the Ministry of Family and Social Services acknowledges the difficulty in making this difference.

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According to the definition provided by the Association of Couple and Family Therapies (ÇATED), relationship therapy is a mental health discipline that asserts that the communication patterns resulting from psychological issues are the root cause of relationship problems (Algan, 2016).

The situation in Turkey is same. Family counseling and family therapy lack unambiguous demarcations and differentiations. Professionals in the sector categorize their practice as counseling rather than therapy (Korkut 2001).

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF FAMILY COUNSELING IN THE WORLD AND TURKEY

The history of Family Counseling worldwide may be categorized into two distinct periods: pre-1940 and post-1940. Prior to 1940, the primary theories used were behaviorist theory and psychoanalysis. These ideologies focused only on the individual and neglected the family. The exclusion of the family by some institutions posed challenges to the development of family therapy (Galdding 2013). Prior to the 1940s, the cultural belief in self-reliance and the tendency to seek assistance from physicians and clergy posed challenges to the development of family therapy (Karataş, 2016).

During the second phase, which started in the 1940s, significant advancements occurred in the field of family counseling, particularly in America and Europe. These five fundamental advancements have made a substantial contribution to the progress of family therapy (Golden, 2000). The following items are:

System theory posits that changes in one component of a system have an impact on the whole system.

Studies have shown that dysfunctional family structures may contribute to the development of schizophrenia in individuals from schizophrenic households.

- Couple therapy has been developed to address the difficulties that both couples have with each other.
- The child guidance movement emphasizes the need of taking the whole family into

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account when providing direction to children.

Group therapy has arisen as a tool for addressing and treating group dynamics.

Prior to 1940, treatment techniques underwent a transition when several schools of thought emerged, and this trend lasted even beyond the 1940s.

Family Therapy in Turkey and the World

While the notion of family has been around for a long time, family therapy is a relatively recent development. Family therapy is a kind of psychotherapy that is administered by a trained therapist. It is a contemporary therapeutic approach that is now being used. It is referred to by several names in different nations. Family counseling, couple and family therapy, marriage and family therapy, family systems therapy, and family therapy are some of the most often used terms to describe this kind of treatment. Within our nation, the term often used is "family counseling" as a result of the research conducted by the Ministry of Family and Social Policies. The notion of family therapy refers to the therapeutic treatment of family groupings. In contrast to individual psychotherapy, family therapy focuses on treating the family unit as a whole, seeing it as a system rather than focusing just on the person. It is based on the concept that the whole is more significant than the individual components and examines the dynamics of the family as a unified entity. It explores the dynamics of family functioning and the interpersonal relationships among family members.

In family therapy, the quality and functions of the relationship among family members are just as significant as the unique attributes of each family member. The primary objective of family therapy is to provide effective resolutions for the issues encountered by the family unit. This therapeutic approach aims to facilitate healthy communication among family members, equip them with the essential abilities to comprehend one another accurately, address disputes, and establish appropriate limits. Family therapy originated in the 20th century. Nevertheless, upon casual examination, it becomes apparent that its history extends somewhat longer. Although lacking scientific methodologies and a systematic approach, it is recognized that in ancient

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tribes, elderly individuals with wisdom assumed a regulating function in the bilateral interactions among adults and played a pivotal part in the teaching of young individuals and children. Upon examining its formal progression, America emerges as the foremost nation, with the Second World War serving as the catalyst. Family therapy did not exist in America until the 1940s.

The catalyst for the process was the enrollment of women in universities. Female university students predominantly expressed a preference for enrolling in courses pertaining to family and domestic matters. Lessons were meticulously organized, prompting an increasing number of specialists to contemplate this topic. Comprehensive literature was generated on this subject, and gradually, journals dedicated to this subject emerged. Subsequently, local governments introduced the establishment of "local family officers". The local family officers conducted a regional tour, where they interviewed families and provided information on family dynamics and living. The establishment of departments specializing in "marriage psychological counseling" at schools has led to an acceleration of both practical and theoretical applications in this field. Following that, organizations dedicated to family and marital counseling/therapy were created, institutions focusing on family relations were founded, and the area of professional marriage psychological counseling emerged.

Nevertheless, the primary catalyst for the development of family therapy was the Second World War and the subsequent changes in social dynamics. War and its repercussions have inflicted substantial pain and hardship onto many families in the United States. A significant number of males departed from their residences and families, while a considerable number of women joined the workforce. Unexpectedly, the family structure underwent a transformation, resulting in significant pecuniary and spiritual losses for families. Providing psychological assistance has become necessary for families and people who are experiencing trauma, suffering, and changes. In 1946, the United States enacted a significant legislation known as the National Mental Health Act. This legislation mandated that states must give the necessary financial support for the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of mental diseases. Subsequently, this statute included mental health treatments for families, leading to the development of various forms of

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psychotherapy, including family therapies. Consequently, the first need was to have skilled individuals to operate in this domain. As a consequence, training facilities and academic programs for family therapy were established in the 1960s. During the 1960s and 70s, Europe had significant advancements in the area of family therapy. The advancements seen during this period, particularly in Italy and England, made substantial contributions to the progress of the discipline, leading to the global dissemination of family counseling.

During the period from 2000 to 2010, the field has been thoroughly developed and established. Currently, there are professional organizations and associations dedicated to family therapy on every continent throughout Europe, America, Asia, Africa, and Australia. Examining the evolution of family therapy in our nation, it becomes evident that it began to acquire significance between 2000 and 2010, aligning with its global growth. However, its popularity has particularly surged in recent years. Various causes have led to this surge in popularity. One reason is that the majority of people now belong to Generation X, a generation that values uniqueness, personal needs, happiness, and places significance on difference and career planning.

These hereditary traits play a crucial role in influencing social and family dynamics. The current generation has seen changes in social structure, family structure, and the prevalence of parallel marriages, as opposed to the preceding generation. While some perspectives attribute this phenomenon to factors like the decline of the Turkish family structure and the breakdown of the marital system, it is more accurate to describe it as a transformation that aligns with the characteristics of the current generation. Change does not always signify progress, nor does it invariably signify decline. The transformation of society and family is contingent upon the changes encountered at the individual level, and this phenomenon is unavoidable. In this scenario, the functional approach should not include reverting to the past, but rather acknowledging the disparities and effectively handling the present circumstances. As change is an ongoing process. The rise in the popularity of family therapy in recent years may be attributed to the research conducted by the Ministry of Family and Social Policies. The Ministry has implemented several significant training and support initiatives, including pre-marriage education, family education, and divorce counseling. Simultaneously, there was a growing need

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for skilled professionals in this domain, leading to the emergence of a new job sector. Consequently, several colleges and educational institutions-initiated training programs focused on family counseling.

Regrettably, the surge in popularity of family therapy in our nation may be attributed not to a growing need from families seeking treatment, but rather to the rising number of professionals seeking training in this field. As per the recent ministry regulation, individuals can qualify for family counselor training by completing a minimum of a four-year undergraduate degree in child development, social work, psychology, psychological counseling and guidance, nursing, or medicine. Put simply, individuals from professional groups without therapeutic training or infrastructure now have access to the road of becoming a therapist. Amidst the many ongoing arguments around treatment, including those between psychiatrists and psychologists, this recently introduced training program seems to intensify these discussions further. These regions, characterized by the absence of established regulations and clear demarcations of professional limits, will be a topic of debate in the next years.

To mitigate these conversations, it is essential to promptly establish job descriptions, delineate professional boundaries, and define regions of power. Additionally, it is crucial to promptly pass professional legislation. It is important to have a firm understanding of the distinctions between "Family Counseling" and "Family Social Support Counselling" and their respective job descriptions.

As part of the 61st Government Program, the Family Social Support Program (ASDEP) employs Family Social Support Consultants to conduct on-site examinations of families by visiting their residences. The organization provides essential information and advice services to fulfill the requirements of people and families, particularly in the areas of health, education, and employment, as well as social services and aid.

When we refer to a Family Counselor, we are describing a therapist who conducts interviews with family members using fundamental interview methods and concepts. The counselor follows a specific strategy and employs a range of strategies to address and resolve issues. It is evident that there are two distinct work positions that arise, each with its own unique job

descriptions and requisite qualifications. When examining the trajectory of family therapy in Turkey and its potential implications, we see a contentious and enigmatic scenario. Undoubtedly, for a firm to operate efficiently, it is essential to have a strong foundation. It is crucial to establish precise definitions and establish clear limits to prevent any misuse, professional infringements, and disputes. Additionally, it is essential to ensure that the system is managed by competent and suitable individuals. Most significantly, families should be able to get the utmost advantage from this system. I am certain that once this basis is established firmly, family therapy will gain broad recognition as a legitimate and dependable system, leading to several families benefiting from its implementation (Kalkankılıç, 2018).

Consultancy System and Operation in Turkey

Family therapy services in Turkey are in their early stages. Recently, there has been an increasing recognition of the need for family counseling services. As a result, both private psychological counseling centers and authorized public institutions and organizations have started conducting pilot studies in this field. These initiatives, operating under the name of "Family Counseling Centers," have become more prevalent due to relevant regulations and laws. Recently, there has been a growing inclination towards scientific research in the subject of family counseling in our country. As a result, colleges have begun offering a course specifically dedicated to "Family Counseling". Additionally, training in the field of family counseling is provided as a dedicated department within many institutions' master's degrees, both thesis and non-thesis, known as the "Family Counseling Program". Psychological advice and counseling are included as part of the curriculum in master's and/or doctorate programs offered by social work, psychology, and health sciences departments in some institutions.

Who Can Become a Family Counselor in Turkey?

Aktaş (2015) offers a unique take on the subject: Family counseling, often known as family therapy, is a kind of therapy that focuses on improving communication and resolving conflicts

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within a family unit. Counselling refers to the provision of support and guidance services by qualified professionals, such as psychologists, psychological counselors, and social workers, to individuals, groups, or whole families.

Furthermore, those who have completed their undergraduate studies, as mentioned in the first paragraph of Article 14 in the Official Gazette No. 28401 dated 04.09.2012, are eligible to pursue a career as family counselors.

According to Article 14, individuals who have completed a minimum of four-year undergraduate programs in social work, psychology, sociology, psychological counseling and guidance, medicine, nursing, or child development are required to complete a total of 450 hours of practical experience. Out of these hours, at least 300 hours must be theoretical and at least 30 hours must be supervised. The practical experience must be approved by either the Ministry of National Education, the Council of Higher Education, or a recognized university.

Can be granted the designation of family consultant as stated in the Official Gazette of 2012.

What are the differences between family counseling and family therapy?

ADU is an emerging service type that is currently being developed in Turkey. Due to this factor, despite some professionals drawing a differentiation between "counseling" and "therapy," there exists a conceptual and content uncertainty about "Family Counseling" and "Family Therapy" in our nation. Korkut (2001, p. 115) states that Family Counseling is at the junction of Family Therapy and Psychological Counseling Model. However, there is still no clear agreement on this area of research. Furthermore, Family Counseling is a briefer kind of treatment compared to Family Therapy. ADU aims to enhance the family structure without altering it, in contrast to therapeutic approaches.

Family therapy serves the purposes of offering understanding and consciousness, reorganizing and growth. Family therapy is a psychological support service that aims to foster a healthy communication environment among all members of a family. These services address the complex issues associated to the psychological and social well-being of families, specifically

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focusing on the dynamics within the family and their interactions with the environment. They need specialized knowledge and skills to effectively address the structural, functional, and developmental aspects of these challenges.

Family therapy has biopsychosocial healing and therapeutic qualities. Family therapy, in this sense, refers to a comprehensive therapeutic approach that addresses the biological, psychological, and social aspects of individuals within a family unit. Its primary goal is to diagnose and treat mental diseases, if required, in order to establish a conducive and healthy family environment. (ASAGEM, 2008, pages 27-28).

Positive Aspects and Limitations of Family Counseling in Turkey

The profession of family counseling is emerging in Turkey. The development of family communication difficulties and child-family connections in Turkey is still in its early stages. Providing guidance to people with psychological issues, offering support to families facing communication difficulties, addressing conflicts within families due to different causes, addressing violence against women, and addressing violence stemming from traditional ceremonies that still have influence in some areas, may have detrimental effects on the structure of families. Family counselors play a crucial role in addressing social difficulties, therefore facilitating the work of psychologists and providing a sociological lens to better understand the family structure. However, due to the absence of a definitive professional age, there is a prevailing belief that everyone has a right to voice their opinions in this subject, leading to misunderstanding.

FAMILY COUNSELING SYSTEM AND ITS OPERATION IN AMERICA

Medical Family Therapy in Primary Care: An Integration Framework

The profession of marriage and family therapy (MFT) and the emerging subspecialty of medical family therapy (MedFT) are expanding and developing within the current healthcare system. Integrated primary care (IPC) is a well-suited setting for professionals who have a focus on

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relationships and systems. Despite the abundance of research on collaborative health care systems, several gaps still exist: The challenges in the current models include: (a) the absence of models that integrate various diseases or demographic populations, (b) the absence of models that can be used regardless of the progression of the disease (i.e., decline, stabilization, recovery), and (c) the absence of IPC models that explicitly involve MedFT/MFTs as mental health providers within the system. To address these shortcomings, the authors propose an Interprofessional Collaboration (IPC) framework that utilizes MedFTs / MFTs. This framework is designed to be applicable across different populations and diseases. Additionally, the authors provide a model for implementing the framework, independent of the progression of the illness. The approach employs contact ethnography to document the interactions between MedFTs, frontline medical practitioners, and patients throughout the whole process, starting from the first contact and leading up to the coordination of a common treatment plan. The recommendations for future research studies on the use of MedFTs in integrated primary care have been broadened within the three worldview frameworks, as discussed in the works of Peek and Springer (2008) and Peek and Heinrich (1995, 1998) in collaborative medicine case studies.

Integrated Maintenance

While this article does not cover the whole range of integrated care vocabulary, it is important to briefly explore the concepts that are significant to the implementation and development of integrated care models. Peek's (2011) endeavor to establish a universal language, in the form of a dictionary, for this particular type of care is highly commendable. This initiative categorizes mental health/health care collaboration into nine distinct areas: (a) team composition, (b) level of collaboration/integration, (c) target population, (d) method of population identification, (e) program scale or maturity, (f) score level centrality/involvement, (g) level of office application design and reliability, (h) business model/funding, and (i) ability to collect and utilize application data. The factors b (degree of collaboration) and c (target population) are particularly relevant to the subject at hand. Peek and colleagues have previously proposed in the literature that innovators must also give careful consideration to the clinical, operational,

and financial aspects that influence healthcare and ultimately determine the feasibility of integrated care models (Peek 2008; Peek and Heinrich 1995, 1998). It is worth mentioning that the term IC often pertains to the collaboration between mental and medical health practitioners, while integrated primary care (IPC) explicitly refers to this process in primary care settings.

Level of Collaboration or Integration

This dimension, as defined by Peek (2011), encompasses a synthesis of several research that not only examine the collaboration between mental health and medical practitioners (Blount, 2003), but also explore the interconnectedness of their organizational cultures and professional relationships (Doherty et al., 1996). Blount initially categorized the connections between mental health and medical services as either coordinated, co-located, or integrated. This classification encompassed factors such as the physical proximity and level of communication between medical and mental health professionals, as well as the extent to which patient treatment plans were harmonized. A synthesis of these studies conducted by Peek reveals three distinct types of relationships: coordinated, co-located, and integrated. In the coordinated relationship, providers are located separately, with limited communication and individual treatment plans for patients. In the co-located relationship, providers are located together, leading to more frequent communication, cross-referral of patients, and some shared organizational culture. Lastly, the integrated relationship involves co-locating providers, frequent face-to-face communication regarding patients, shared treatment plans, and a harmonious organizational culture.

Positive Aspects and Limitations of Family Counseling in America

The aim is to focus on the whole range of different patient demographics, diagnoses, and challenges that primary care clinicians encounter (Peek et al., 2009; Peek, 2011; Robinson and Reiter, 2007; Robinson and Strosahl, 2009), also known as horizontal integration. Considering this gap, the objective of this research was two-fold: (a) to provide a comprehensive care

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framework that promotes cooperation between behavioral health providers (BHP) and primary care physicians (PCP) and (b) to define a care system that utilizes MedFTs/MFTs as BHPs within this framework.

Unique Contributions of MEDFTs

The core focus of family therapy, including medical family therapy, is the recognition of the significance and key role of connections and systems in every area of an individual's life (Doherty et al., 1994; Linville et al., 2007; Tyndall et al., 2010). The distinctive aspect of systemic thinking lies in its relational lens, which distinguishes MedFT from other mental health professions. MedFT functions as a BHP in an IPC context, setting it apart from any other profession in the field. MedFTs demonstrate their relational emphasis via two main approaches: (a) their approach to discussing issues and solutions, and (b) their management of patient-provider interactions.

Regarding the analysis of issues and their corresponding resolutions, this research noticed that MedFTs consistently prioritize the importance of relationships, whether it is the connection between the patient, their family, and their social support, or the relationship between the patient and the healthcare professional. This implies that the lack of adherence by a patient is not only considered in terms of their own motivation, but also in relation to how their family, friends, and primary care physician may either assist or impede the patient in reaching their desired objectives (for example, the patient's spouse may assist them in routinely taking insulin). Despite the patient's better health, the enlargement was still seen. This enabled MedFT to emphasize and strengthen the patient's own achievement of success, as well as to explore connections that were especially advantageous for the patient in this context.

FAMILY COUNSELING SYSTEM AND ITS OPERATION IN GERMANY

Germany now allows for the formalization of educational consulting services. Reflect about a longstanding custom that has endured for more than a century. All education and family

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counseling centers today are privately owned, with the first institutions being pioneers in this field. For instance, in major cities of Germany like Fürstennheim and Seif, there are private doctors who established therapeutic education counseling centers. One example is the 1903 center in Hamburg, known as the "Outpatient clinic for medical-pedagogical child research, educational counseling, and medical training treatment" in Berlin. One of the main differences between these facilities and today's educational counseling centers is that they were primarily focused on medical aspects and the work done there was mostly part-time or volunteer (Presting 1991).

During the period spanning from the early 1950s to the post-World War II decades, there were attempts to create a complete network. These efforts were initiated in the late 1970s.

Since the early 1980s, educational counseling facilities have been present across the nation. However, the growth of this network of counseling centers has remained stagnant for a prolonged period of time. This statement indicates that despite the growing need for parenting and family therapy, there has been no increase in the availability of counseling services over the last thirty years (Menne, 2008). Cost concerns and austerity measures have led to employment cuts in some locations (Menne / Schilling / Gollias 2006). Germany now allows for the formalization of educational consulting services. All education and family counseling facilities today have been privatized, making them fully owned and operated by commercial entities. Educational and family counseling specialists often possess one or more supplementary therapeutic certifications, particularly in the field of family therapy. According to Menne (2008), half of all professions now undergo family therapy or systems training.

Positive Aspects and Limitations of Family Counseling in Germany

Obtaining assistance is facilitated by the institutional integration of local advice centers into people's everyday lives and their regular interaction with individuals. In Germany, there are several institutions such as nearby schools, after-school care centers, kindergartens, residences, and other social organizations that facilitate the integration of individuals into their everyday life (Hensen / Körner, 2005).

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The endorsement of family counseling systems, due to their close connection with everyday life concerns, has resulted in the advancement of this subject in Germany.

FAMILY COUNSELING SYSTEM AND ITS OPERATION IN TUNISIA

It gained renown for accurately reflecting the spirit of the Tunisian revolt in January 2011. The current term used to refer to this period of time is the Arab Spring. A subjective structure remains in flux as long as conflicts stemming from the internal realm and pertaining to intersubjectivities within the partnership, family, and social group reverberate, interfere, mutually resolve, or exacerbate. Being linked necessitates an interpersonal existence that promotes individual subjectivity. The second facet, known as the social, refers to those elements of one's identity that are intangible and cannot be recognized outside of the social context. The subject undergoes transformation and realization via these links and their many combinations. Undoubtedly, if change and instability are not well managed and controlled, there is a significant likelihood of encountering violent dangers.

We shall address this issue by providing commentary on the following clinical case within the Tunisian cultural framework. It should be observed that the latter is characterized by a strong and widespread collectivism in the structure of family and social connections (Ghorbal, 1981; Yahyaoui, 2005; Mokdad Zmitri, 2016). However, it also coexists with increasing individualism, which brings in conservative aspects, postmodernity, and modern technology. It combines the features of postmodernity with the mixture of different elements that is typical of evolving social environments and times of transition.

has significantly changed the norms of Tunisian society, which is highly characterized by sexism. In a conventional patriarchal culture, a limited number of women received education, and the number decreased even more when they reached puberty. The house served as the primary living area for women and girls. Access to public spaces was restricted to Moorish baths, family visits, and wedding festivities, which were particularly appealing to parents arranging marriages for their children. The responsibilities of young women included domestic tasks like as cleaning, cooking, and tending to their many siblings, all while they awaited a

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potential suitor with whom they would enter into marriage, sometimes without prior acquaintance.

The Tunisian lady swiftly emerged as an exemplar for women's rights and liberties. Undoubtedly, it was not feasible for her circumstances as a spouse and family to be promptly and impartially aligned with the law. The predicament of Miss M., which is not unique, highlights the significant consequences that arise from the disconnect between political ideologies and personal beliefs on spouses and families. Policies that are both feminist and totalitarian. Bourguiba and later Ben Ali both safeguarded women's rights, with Ben Ali further enhancing them. Nevertheless, the political exploitation of women has oscillated between extremes and persists in current intense discussions, influenced by the policies of the governing parties that have experienced a significant transformation since the 2011 uprising.

Positive Aspects and Limitations of Family Counseling in Tunisia

This society is continuously negotiating the regulation of family connections within an outdated cultural framework, while progressively moving away from "sexism" and embracing the present trends of globalization and democracy. The new "family environment" that it opens into is characterized by fewer apparent and preconceived links between genders and generations (Zimitri, 2019).

Upon the implementation of the aforementioned rule, the prevailing state of "social tyranny" that had previously dictated the dynamics between genders, the handling of gender distinctions, familial connections, and the boundary between internal and external realms, was immediately confronted. Granting women novel and audacious liberties at that time period also included a certain degree of danger. This occurred due to the severe and significant shift, resulting in Tunisia being marginalized among its Arab and Muslim counterparts (Zmitri, 2019).

The establishment of the family counseling system in Tunisia has resulted in the distinction between Arab and Muslim brothers. Additionally, this system has been recognized as a significant advancement for women who experience abuse in Tunisia.

FAMILY COUNSELING SYSTEM AND ITS OPERATION IN CHINA

Family therapy, a kind of psychotherapy, was developed in the United States during the mid-20th century. It has since been adopted by Chinese counselors and therapists and is now widely used in psychological counseling and treatment. Family therapy aligns with the evolution of Chinese family culture, which is shaped by both traditional Chinese values and Western influences (Li Ling, 2004).

Clinical psychologists have embraced treatment as the fourth influential factor in the realm of psychotherapy. Within the realm of family therapy, several theoretical schools have been established, and local researchers have contributed several systemic family treatments. Structural family therapy is a significant subdivision of family therapy. As structural therapy training courses have been developed, domestic scientists have also started incorporating this treatment into their clinical practice (Cao Lili, 2005).

The symptoms of symptomatic patients were proven to be alleviated by structural family therapy, indicating its suitability for Chinese families. Notably, this therapeutic approach has shown remarkable effectiveness in addressing psychiatric illnesses among teenagers and marital crises. Structural family therapy is a significant subdivision of family therapy that is well-suited for diagnosing and treating family issues within Chinese culture (Cao Lili, 2005).

Positive Aspects and Limitations of Family Counseling in China

The implementation of a treatment model in China has offered families an effective approach for addressing psychological diseases and marital difficulties among teenagers. The use of structural family therapy in China is congruent with the evolution of China's family culture. This proportion may also be readily utilized in China.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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Family therapy has been more prominent in addressing issues related to family communication, division of roles, children's communication within the family, and the referral of individuals with psychological and physical difficulties to appropriate professionals. While it may be referred to as family therapy or family counseling in different nations, it cannot be classified as either family counseling or a therapist. It facilitates the resolution of familial issues. Family systems, derived from many societal frameworks, may encounter challenges related to violence, issues with role allocation, and communication. It also impacts psychological and physical issues.

In such instances, the duty of family counselors is to provide assistance to families by using different strategies to address difficulties pertaining to family dynamics, such as communication and the allocation of family duties. If the individual exhibits signs of a psychological or physical condition, it is advisable to direct them to a doctor who specializes in the area of psychology. When violence occurs, it is imperative to engage the assistance of social workers.

Family issues might differ based on the social framework of each nation. Therefore, certain nations prioritize couples' treatment, while others prioritize addressing violence or child and family issues. For instance, family counselors mostly focus on relationship therapy and psychological issues in nations like America and Germany, while they primarily address violence, family dynamics, and children in countries such as Tunisia, China, and Turkey. The variability of this condition is contingent upon the social and cultural framework and requirements of each individual country.

RESTRICTION

No restrictions were stated in the research.

NOTIFICATION

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

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